

A new existence result of unique solution for class of fractional differential equations involving sequential operators and nonlinear perturbations in weighted Sobolev spaces

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Abstract

In this work, we investigated a class of fractional differential boundary value problems characterized by sequential operators and nonlinear perturbations. By converting the original system into an equivalent integral formulation, we can apply Banach's fixed point theorem to study the existence of a unique solution to the system under appropriate assumptions on the nonlinearities. The results presented here not only unify several previously known results but also extend them to a broader class of fractional systems involving sequential operators.

Keywords: Riemann–Liouville fractional differential equation, non-local conditions, weighted Sobolev spaces, fixed point theorem, Mittag-Leffler function, fractional derivatives.

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1 Introduction

The fact that fractional-order derivatives are better suited to describing various real materials and that the use of fractional calculus reduces the number of parameters needed in modeling

are two reasons why fractional calculus has recently gained increasing attention. As a result, many phenomena in various applied science and engineering domains, including control, dielectric polarization, fluid mechanics, electrochemistry, bioengineering, viscoelasticity, chaotic dynamics, etc., are better described by differential equations involving fractional derivatives; see [11, 21, 20]. Specifically, the analysis of stability is one of the most fundamental problems in system theory. The stability of fractional-order systems has been the subject of numerous studies in recent years; see [7, 8, 9].

The authors of [5] investigated whether a Riemann–Liouville fractional boundary value problem admits positive solutions in a Sobolev space.

$$D_{0+}^{\alpha} \varpi(\kappa) + \mathcal{F}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa), D_{0+}^{\gamma} \varpi(\kappa)) = 0, \quad 0 < \kappa < 1,$$

$$\lim_{\kappa \rightarrow 0} D_{0+}^{i-\alpha} \varpi(\kappa) = 0, \quad i = 2, \dots, n, \quad \varpi(1) = \sum_{k=0}^m \lambda_k I_{0+}^{\beta} \varpi(n_k),$$

where I_{0+}^{β} denotes the usual Riemann–Liouville fractional integral, $\mathcal{F} : [0, 1] \times \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$, and D_{0+}^{α} represent the standard Riemann–Liouville fractional derivative of order α , with $n - 1 \leq \alpha < n$, $n \geq 4$, and $0 < \gamma < 1$; see [2, 12, 16, 19].

The authors established the existence and uniqueness of solutions by employing Schauder’s fixed-point theorem in combination with the method of upper and lower solutions.

The existence and uniqueness of solutions to integro-differential equations involving the Riemann–Liouville fractional derivative were investigated by Ali et al. [3].

$$\begin{cases} D_{0+}^{\alpha} \varpi(\kappa) = \mathcal{F}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa), D_{0+}^{\alpha-1} \varpi(\kappa)), \quad \kappa \geq 0 \\ D_{0+}^{\alpha-1} \varpi(0) = x_0, \quad I_{0+}^{2-\alpha} \varpi(0) = x_1. \end{cases}$$

where $x_0, x_1 \in \mathbb{R}$, $1 < \alpha \leq 2$, and D_{0+}^{α} denote the Riemann–Liouville fractional derivative of orders α and $\mathcal{F} : \mathbb{R}_+ \times \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$; see [13, 14, 15].

Inspired by the aforementioned contributions in fractional calculus and fixed-point theory, we focus on a new class of sequential fractional integro-differential equations involving functional perturbations in both the differential term and the boundary conditions. Our objective is to establish rigorous conditions that guarantee the existence and uniqueness of solutions for this class of problems.

To achieve this, we first rewrite the original formulation as an equivalent integral equation and subsequently apply Banach’s contraction principle to derive the main results. In particular, we consider the following fractional sequential problem:

$$\begin{cases} D_{0+}^{\alpha} \{ \varpi(\kappa) + \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) \} = \mathcal{F}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)), & \kappa \geq 0, \\ D_{0+}^{\alpha-1} (\varpi(0) + \mathcal{E}(0, \varpi(0))) = \varpi_0, & \varpi(1) = \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \varpi(\xi_i), \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

where $\varpi_0, \sigma_i \in \mathbb{R}$, $\xi_i \in \mathbb{R}^+$, and $1 < \alpha \leq 2$, D_{0+}^α denotes the Riemann–Liouville fractional derivative of order α and $\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{E} : \mathbb{R}_+ \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the necessary preliminary concepts and auxiliary results. Section 3 is devoted to the formulation and proof of our main existence and uniqueness theorems. An illustrative example is given in Section 4.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, let us recall some basics of fractional calculus.

Definition 2.1. [10, 17] The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral of order α for a function $\mathcal{F} \in L^1[0, b]$ is defined as

$$I_{0+}^\alpha \mathcal{F}(\kappa) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^\kappa (\kappa - s)^{\alpha-1} \mathcal{F}(s) ds. \quad (2.1)$$

Definition 2.2. [17, 18] The Riemann Liouville fractional derivative of order α of a function \mathcal{F} is given by,

$$D_{0+}^\alpha \mathcal{F}(\kappa) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \alpha)} \left(\frac{d}{d\kappa} \right)^n \int_0^\kappa (\kappa - s)^{n-\alpha-1} \mathcal{F}(s) ds, \quad (2.2)$$

where $n = [\alpha] + 1$, $[\alpha]$ denotes the integer part of α .

Definition 2.3. [10, 18] The Mittag-Leffler function is defined by

$$E_{\alpha, \lambda}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + \lambda)}, \quad (z \in \mathbb{C}, \mathcal{R}(\lambda), \mathcal{R}(\alpha) > 0).$$

Lemma 2.1. [10] If $\mathcal{F} \in L^1[0, b]$, then

$$D_{0+}^\alpha I_{0+}^\alpha \mathcal{F}(\kappa) = \mathcal{F}(\kappa).$$

Lemma 2.2. [1, 4] Let $z, \kappa \in \mathbb{R}$, then

1. $E_{\alpha, \lambda}(z) \leq \frac{1}{a} z^{\frac{1-\lambda}{\alpha}} e^{z^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}}$, $0 < \alpha < 2, \lambda > 1$.
2. $I_{0+}^\alpha e^{\lambda \kappa} = \kappa^\alpha E_{1, \alpha+1}(\lambda \kappa)$, $(\lambda > 0, \alpha > 0)$.
3. $\frac{1}{\alpha \Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^\kappa (\kappa - s)^{\alpha-1} e^{\lambda s} ds = e^{\lambda a} (\kappa - a)^\alpha E_{1, \alpha+1}(\lambda(\kappa - a))$, $(a \neq 0, \lambda > 0)$.

From [10], we denote by $L_{1,\omega}$ the space of functions \mathcal{F} with an exponential weight $\omega > 0$ on \mathbb{R} by defining the norm as follows:

$$L_{1,\omega}(0, 1) = \left\{ \mathcal{F} : \|\mathcal{F}\|_{1,\omega} = \int_0^1 e^{-\omega s} |\mathcal{F}(s)| ds < \infty \right\}. \quad (2.3)$$

From [6, 10], we define the weighted fractional Sobolev space as follows:

$$W_{\omega,0+}^{\alpha,1}(0, 1) = \{ \mathcal{F} : \mathcal{F} \in L_{1,\omega}(0, 1), D_{0+}^{\alpha} \mathcal{F} \in L_{1,\omega}(0, 1) \} \quad 0 < \alpha < 1. \quad (2.4)$$

Lemma 2.3. $W_{\omega,0+}^{\alpha,1}(0, 1)$ is a Banach space endowed with the norm

$$\|\mathcal{F}\|_{W_{\omega,0+}^{\alpha,1}} = \|\mathcal{F}\|_{1,\omega} + \|D_{0+}^{\alpha} \mathcal{F}\|_{1,\omega}. \quad (2.5)$$

Remark 2.4. The proof of the above lemma is clear, using results in [6, 10].

Lemma 2.5. Let $\rho > 0$, $\gamma = \alpha - 1$ and

$$\mathcal{G}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa), D^{\gamma} \varpi(\kappa)) = -\rho D_{0+}^{\gamma} \left\{ \mathcal{E}(s, \varpi(s)) + \varpi(s) \right\}.$$

Then ϖ is a solution of the Cauchy type problem (1.1) if and only if ϖ is a solution of the Cauchy type problem

$$\begin{cases} D_{0+}^{\gamma} \left\{ \varpi(\kappa) + \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) \right\} = e^{\rho\kappa} \int_0^{\kappa} e^{-\rho s} \left\{ \mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa), D^{\gamma} \varpi(\kappa)) \right\} ds + e^{\rho\kappa} \varpi_0, & \kappa \geq 0, \\ \varpi(1) = \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \varpi(\xi_i). \end{cases} \quad (2.6)$$

Proof. We have

$$\int_0^{\kappa} e^{-\rho s} D_{0+}^{\alpha} \left\{ \varpi(s) + \mathcal{E}(s, \varpi(s)) \right\} ds = \int_0^{\kappa} e^{-\rho s} \mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) ds. \quad (2.7)$$

We use integration by parts; we find

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{\kappa} e^{-\rho s} D_{0+}^{\alpha} \left\{ \varpi(s) + \mathcal{E}(s, \varpi(s)) \right\} ds \\ &= e^{-\rho\kappa} D_{0+}^{\alpha-1} \left\{ \varpi(\kappa) + \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) \right\} - e^0 D_{0+}^{\alpha-1} \left\{ \varpi(0) + \mathcal{E}(0, \varpi(0)) \right\} \\ &+ \int_0^{\kappa} \rho e^{-\rho s} D_{0+}^{\alpha-1} \left\{ \varpi(s) + \mathcal{E}(s, \varpi(s)) \right\} ds \\ &= e^{-\rho\kappa} D_{0+}^{\alpha-1} \left\{ \varpi(\kappa) + \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) \right\} - \varpi_0 + \rho \int_0^{\kappa} e^{-\rho s} D_{0+}^{\alpha-1} \left\{ \varpi(s) + \mathcal{E}(s, \varpi(s)) \right\} ds. \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$D_{0+}^{\alpha-1} \left\{ \varpi(\kappa) + \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) \right\} = e^{\rho\kappa} \int_0^\kappa e^{-\rho s} \mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + e^{\rho\kappa} \varpi_0 - \rho e^{\rho\kappa} \int_0^\kappa e^{-\rho s} D_{0+}^{\alpha-1} \left\{ \varpi(s) + \mathcal{E}(s, \varpi(s)) \right\} ds$$

Take $\gamma = \alpha - 1$, yields:

$$\begin{aligned} D_{0+}^\gamma \left\{ \varpi(\kappa) + \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) \right\} &= e^{\rho\kappa} \int_0^\kappa e^{-\rho s} \mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + e^{\rho\kappa} \varpi_0 \\ &\quad - \rho e^{\rho\kappa} \int_0^\kappa e^{-\rho s} D_{0+}^\gamma \left\{ \varpi(s) + \mathcal{E}(s, \varpi(s)) \right\} ds \\ &= e^{\rho\kappa} \int_0^\kappa e^{-\rho s} \left\{ \mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa), D^\gamma \varpi(\kappa)) \right\} ds + e^{\rho\kappa} \varpi_0. \end{aligned}$$

Conversely, we replace κ with 0 in (2.6), then $D_{0+}^{\alpha-1} \left\{ \varpi(0) + \mathcal{E}(0, \varpi(0)) \right\} = \varpi_0$.

By (2.6), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} e^{-\rho\kappa} D_{0+}^\gamma \left\{ \varpi(\kappa) + \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) \right\} &= \int_0^\kappa e^{-\rho s} [\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D^\gamma \varpi(s))] ds + \varpi_0 \\ &= \int_0^\kappa e^{-\rho s} [\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) - \rho D_{0+}^\gamma \left\{ \varpi(s) + \mathcal{E}(s, \varpi(s)) \right\}] ds \\ &\quad + D_{0+}^\gamma \left\{ \varpi(0) + \mathcal{E}(0, \varpi(0)) \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^\kappa e^{-\rho s} \mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) ds &= e^{-\rho\kappa} D_{0+}^\gamma \left\{ \varpi(\kappa) + \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) \right\} - D_{0+}^\gamma \left\{ \varpi(0) + \mathcal{E}(0, \varpi(0)) \right\} \\ &\quad + \rho \int_0^\kappa e^{-\rho s} D_{0+}^\gamma \left\{ \varpi(s) + \mathcal{E}(s, \varpi(s)) \right\} ds. \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\int_0^\kappa e^{-\rho s} \mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) ds = \int_0^\kappa e^{-\rho s} D_{0+}^{\gamma+1} \left\{ \varpi(s) + \mathcal{E}(s, \varpi(s)) \right\} ds.$$

We replace γ with $\alpha - 1$; we get

$$\mathcal{F}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) = D_{0+}^\alpha \left\{ \varpi(\kappa) + \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) \right\}.$$

Which completes the proof. □

Lemma 2.6. ϖ is a solution to the problem (2.6) if and only if ϖ is a solution to the following fractional integral equation

$$\begin{aligned} \varpi(\kappa) &= \int_0^\kappa (\kappa - s)^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho(\kappa - s)) [\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s))] ds + \varpi_0 \kappa^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho\kappa) - \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) \\ &+ \frac{\kappa^{\gamma-1}}{1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}} \left\{ - \int_0^1 (1 - s)^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho(1 - s)) [\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s))] ds \right. \\ &+ \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \int_0^{\xi_i} (\xi_i - s)^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho(\xi_i - s)) [\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s))] ds \\ &\left. + \varpi_0 \left[\sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho\xi_i) - E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho) \right] - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \mathcal{E}(\xi_i, \varpi(\xi_i)) + \mathcal{E}(1, \varpi(1)) \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let ϖ be a solution to the problem (2.6).

We have

$$\begin{aligned} D_{0+}^\gamma \left\{ \varpi(\kappa) + \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) \right\} &= e^{\rho\kappa} \int_0^\kappa e^{-\rho s} \left\{ \mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D^\gamma \varpi(s)) \right\} ds + e^{\rho\kappa} \varpi_0 \\ \varpi(\kappa) + \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) - c_1 \kappa^{\gamma-1} &= I_{0+}^\gamma e^{\rho\kappa} \int_0^\kappa e^{-\rho s} \left\{ \mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D^\gamma \varpi(s)) \right\} ds + \varpi_0 I_{0+}^\gamma e^{\rho\kappa}. \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \varpi(\kappa) &= \frac{1}{\alpha(\gamma)} \int_0^\kappa (\kappa - s)^{\gamma-1} e^{\rho s} \int_0^s [\mathcal{F}(\tau, \varpi(\tau)) + \mathcal{G}(\tau, \varpi(\tau), D^\gamma \varpi(\tau))] e^{-\rho\tau} d\tau ds \\ &+ \varpi_0 I_{0+}^\gamma e^{\rho\kappa} - \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) + c_1 \kappa^{\gamma-1}. \end{aligned} \tag{2.8}$$

Using Fubini's theorem, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \varpi(\kappa) &= \frac{1}{\alpha(\gamma)} \int_0^\kappa \int_\tau^s (\kappa - s)^{\gamma-1} e^{\rho s} ds [\mathcal{F}(\tau, \varpi(\tau)) + \mathcal{G}(\tau, \varpi(\tau), D^\gamma \varpi(\tau))] e^{-\rho\tau} d\tau \\ &+ \varpi_0 I_{0+}^\gamma e^{\rho\kappa} - \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) + c_1 \kappa^{\gamma-1}. \\ &= \int_0^\kappa (\kappa - \tau)^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho(\kappa - \tau)) [\mathcal{F}(\tau, \varpi(\tau)) + \mathcal{G}(\tau, \varpi(\tau), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(\tau))] d\tau \\ &+ \varpi_0 \kappa^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho\kappa) + c_1 \kappa^{\gamma-1} - \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)). \end{aligned}$$

using the second condition ,

$$\begin{aligned} \varpi(1) &= \int_0^1 (1-s)^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho(1-s)) [\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s))] ds \\ &\quad + \varpi_0 E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho) - \mathcal{E}(1, \varpi(1)) + c_1. \\ \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \varpi(\xi_i) &= \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \int_0^{\xi_i} (\xi_i - s)^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho(\xi_i - s)) [\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s))] ds \\ &\quad + \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \varpi_0 \xi_i^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho \xi_i) + \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i c_1 \xi_i^{\gamma-1} - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \mathcal{E}(\xi_i, \varpi(\xi_i)). \end{aligned}$$

Then, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 &= \frac{1}{1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}} \left\{ - \int_0^1 (1-s)^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho(1-s)) [\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s))] ds \right. \\ &\quad + \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \int_0^{\xi_i} (\xi_i - s)^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho(\xi_i - s)) [\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s))] ds \\ &\quad \left. + \varpi_0 \left[\sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho \xi_i) - E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho) \right] - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \mathcal{E}(\xi_i, \varpi(\xi_i)) + \mathcal{E}(1, \varpi(1)) \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Conversely, by (2.8), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \varpi(\kappa) &= \frac{1}{\alpha(\gamma)} \int_0^\kappa (\kappa - \tau)^{\gamma-1} e^{\rho\tau} \int_0^\kappa [\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s))] e^{-\rho s} ds \\ &\quad + I_{0+}^\gamma \varpi_0 e^{\rho\kappa} + c_1 \kappa^{\gamma-1} - \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)). \end{aligned} \tag{2.9}$$

By applying the operator D_{0+}^γ on both sides of (2.9), we find

$$D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(\kappa) = e^{\rho\kappa} \int_0^\kappa [\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s))] e^{-\rho s} ds - D_{0+}^\gamma \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) + \varpi_0 e^{\rho\kappa}. \tag{2.10}$$

We replace κ with 0 in (2.10) and κ with 1 in (2.9); we obtain

$$D_{0+}^{\alpha-1} \{ \varpi(0) + \mathcal{E}(0, \varpi(0)) \} = \varpi_0, \quad \varpi(1) = \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \varpi(\xi_i),$$

,which completes the proof. □

3 Existence and uniqueness results

In this section, we shall present and prove our main results.
 Let us consider the following:

$$\delta'_1 = \left\{ \frac{(1 + \rho^\gamma)\ell}{\rho^\gamma(\rho_1 - \rho)} + \ell' + \frac{\sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| e^{\rho\xi_i} + e^\rho}{|1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}| \rho_1^\gamma \rho^\gamma} \ell \Gamma(\gamma) \right\}, \quad (3.1)$$

$$\delta'_2 = \left\{ \frac{\rho(\ell' + 1) + \rho^\gamma(\rho_1 \ell + \rho)}{\rho^\gamma(\rho_1 - \rho)} + \frac{\sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| e^{\rho\xi_i} + e^\rho}{|1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}| \rho_1^\gamma \rho^\gamma} \rho(\ell' + 1) \Gamma(\gamma) \right\}, \quad (3.2)$$

$$\delta'_3 = \left\{ \frac{\ell(1 + \rho^\gamma) + \rho^\gamma(1 + \rho_1 - \rho)\ell'}{\rho^\gamma(\rho_1 - \rho)} + \frac{\rho^{-\gamma} \left(\frac{\gamma-1}{\rho_1}\right)^{\gamma-1} e^{1-\gamma} [e^\rho + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| e^{\rho\xi_i} \xi_i]}{|1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}|} \ell \right\}, \quad (3.3)$$

$$\delta'_4 = \left\{ \frac{1 + \rho\rho^\gamma(\ell' + 1)}{\rho^\gamma(\rho_1 - \rho)} + \frac{\rho^{-\gamma} \left(\frac{\gamma-1}{\rho_1}\right)^{\gamma-1} e^{1-\gamma} [e^\rho + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| e^{\rho\xi_i} \xi_i]}{|1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}|} \right\} \rho(\ell' + 1), \quad (3.4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \delta'_0 = & + \frac{\Gamma(\gamma)}{|1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}| \rho_1^\gamma \rho^\gamma} \left[\left\{ \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| e^{\rho\xi_i} + e^\rho \right\} \left\{ \frac{M_1}{\rho} + \frac{M_2}{\Gamma(1-\gamma)} \right\} \right. \\ & + |\varpi_0| \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| e^{\rho\xi_i} + |\varpi_0| e^\rho + \frac{\rho^\gamma \rho_1^\gamma}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \left\{ |\mathcal{E}(1, \varpi(1))| + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| |\mathcal{E}(\xi_i, \varpi(\xi_i))| \right\} \\ & \left. + \frac{1 + \rho^\gamma + \rho^\gamma(\rho_1 - \rho)}{\rho_1 \rho^\gamma(\rho_1 - \rho)} M_1 + \frac{\rho + \rho\rho^\gamma(\rho_1 - \rho)}{\rho_1 \rho^\gamma(\rho_1 - \rho) \Gamma(1-\gamma)} M_2 + \frac{|\varpi_0|}{\rho_1(\rho_1 - \rho)}. \right] \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

We consider the following assumptions

(HYP₁) $\mathcal{F}(\cdot, 0), \mathcal{E}(\cdot, 0), D_{0+}^\gamma \mathcal{E}(\cdot, 0) \in L_{1, \rho_1}(\mathbb{R}_+)$.

(HYP₂) There exist two constants ℓ and ℓ' such that

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{F}(\kappa, \varpi) - \mathcal{F}(\kappa, \omega)| &\leq \ell |\varpi - \omega|, & \ell > 0, \\ |\mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi) - \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \omega)| &\leq \ell' |\varpi - \omega|, & \ell' > 0, \end{aligned}$$

for $\kappa \in \mathbb{R}_+$, and $\varpi, \omega \in \mathbb{R}$.

(HYP₃) Let $\mathcal{F}, \mathcal{E} \in L_{1,1}(\mathbb{R})$.

Theorem 3.1. *Let $\rho < \rho_1$. Assume that the assumptions (HYP₁) and (HYP₂) hold. If*

$$\|\varpi - \omega\|_{W_{\rho_1, 0^+}^{\gamma, 1}} < \max\{\delta'_3, \delta'_4\} \|\varpi - \omega\|_{W_{\rho_1, 0^+}^{\gamma, 1}}, \quad (3.6)$$

with

$$\max\{\delta'_3, \delta'_4\} < 1. \quad (3.7)$$

Then the fractional integro-differential problem (2.6) has a unique solution on $W_{\rho_1, 0^+}^{\gamma, 1}$.

Proof. Firstly, we define an operator $\mathcal{Q} : W_{\rho_1, 0^+}^{\gamma, 1} \rightarrow W_{\rho_1, 0^+}^{\gamma, 1}$, by

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{Q}\varpi(\kappa) \\ = & \int_0^\kappa (\kappa - s)^\gamma E_{1, \gamma+1}(\rho(\kappa - s)) [\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0^+}^\gamma \varpi(s))] ds + \varpi_0 \kappa^\gamma E_{1, \gamma+1}(\rho\kappa) - \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) \\ & + \frac{\kappa^{\gamma-1}}{1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}} \left\{ - \int_0^1 (1 - s)^\gamma E_{1, \gamma+1}(\rho(1 - s)) [\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0^+}^\gamma \varpi(s))] ds \right. \\ & + \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \int_0^{\xi_i} (\xi_i - s)^\gamma E_{1, \gamma+1}(\rho(\xi_i - s)) [\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) + \mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0^+}^\gamma \varpi(s))] ds \\ & \left. + \varpi_0 \left[\sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^\gamma E_{1, \gamma+1}(\rho \xi_i) - E_{1, \gamma+1}(\rho) \right] - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \mathcal{E}(\xi_i, \varpi(\xi_i)) + \mathcal{E}(1, \varpi(1)) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

Taking

$$M_1 = \sup \{ |\mathcal{F}(\kappa, 0)| : \kappa \in \mathbb{R}^+ \},$$

and

$$M_2 = \sup \{ |\mathcal{E}(\kappa, 0)| : \kappa \in \mathbb{R}^+ \},$$

and choosing

$$r \leq \frac{\delta'_0}{1 - \max\{\delta'_1, \delta'_2\}}, \quad (3.9)$$

where

$$B_r = \{ \varpi \in W_{\rho_1, 0^+}^{\gamma, 1} : \|\varpi\|_{W_{\rho_1, 0^+}^{\gamma, 1}} \leq r \}.$$

To do this, for $\varpi \in B_r$, and using (HYP₂), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \left| \mathcal{G}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa), D^\gamma \varpi(\kappa)) \right| &= \left| -\rho D_{0+}^\gamma \left\{ \mathcal{E}(s, \varpi(s)) + \varpi(s) \right\} \right| \\
 &= \rho \left| D_{0+}^\gamma \left\{ \mathcal{E}(s, \varpi(s)) - \mathcal{E}(\kappa, 0) + \mathcal{E}(\kappa, 0) + \varpi(s) \right\} \right| \\
 &\leq \rho D_{0+}^\gamma \left\{ \left| \mathcal{E}(s, \varpi(s)) - \mathcal{E}(\kappa, 0) \right| + \left| \mathcal{E}(\kappa, 0) \right| + \left| \varpi(s) \right| \right\} \\
 &\leq \rho D_{0+}^\gamma \left\{ \ell' |\varpi(s)| + |\mathcal{E}(\kappa, 0)| + |\varpi(s)| \right\} \\
 &\leq \frac{\rho M_2}{\Gamma(1-\gamma)} + \rho(\ell' + 1) D_{0+}^\gamma |\varpi|. \tag{3.10}
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, we show that the operator \mathcal{Q} has a fixed point on B_r which represents the unique solution of the problem (2.6).

First step: We have to show that $\mathcal{Q}B_r \subset B_r$, for each $\kappa \in \mathbb{R}_+$ and for any $\varpi \in B_r$.

Let $\varpi \in B_r$. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &|\mathcal{Q}\varpi(\kappa)| \tag{3.11} \\
 &\leq \int_0^\kappa (\kappa - s)^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho(\kappa - s)) \left[|\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s))| + |\mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s))| \right] ds + |\varpi_0| \kappa^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho\kappa) \\
 &\quad + \frac{\kappa^{\gamma-1}}{\left| 1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1} \right|} \left[\int_0^1 (1-s)^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho(1-s)) \left[|\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s))| + |\mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s))| \right] ds \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| \int_0^{\xi_i} (\xi_i - s)^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho(\xi_i - s)) \left[|\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s))| + |\mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s))| \right] ds \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + |\varpi_0| \left[\sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| \xi_i^\gamma E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho\xi_i) + E_{1,\gamma+1}(\rho) \right] + |\mathcal{E}(1, \varpi(1))| + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| |\mathcal{E}(\xi_i, \varpi(\xi_i))| \right] + |\mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa))| \\
 &\leq \int_0^\kappa \rho^{-\gamma} e^{\rho(\kappa-s)} \left\{ |\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, 0)| + |\mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s))| \right\} ds + \int_0^\kappa \rho^{-\gamma} e^{\rho(\kappa-s)} \left\{ |\mathcal{F}(s, 0)| \right\} ds \\
 &\quad + \frac{\kappa^{\gamma-1}}{\left| 1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1} \right|} \left[\int_0^1 \rho^{-\gamma} e^{\rho(1-s)} \left\{ |\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, 0)| + |\mathcal{F}(s, 0)| + |\mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s))| \right\} ds \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| \int_0^{\xi_i} \rho^{-\gamma} e^{\rho(\xi_i-s)} \left\{ |\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, 0)| + |\mathcal{F}(s, 0)| + |\mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s))| \right\} ds \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + |\varpi_0| \left[\sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| \rho^{-\gamma} e^{\rho\xi_i} + \rho^{-\gamma} e^\rho + |\mathcal{E}(1, \varpi(1))| + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| |\mathcal{E}(\xi_i, \varpi(\xi_i))| \right] \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + |\varpi_0| \rho^{-\gamma} e^{\rho\kappa} + |\mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) - \mathcal{E}(\kappa, 0)| + |\mathcal{E}(\kappa, 0)| \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Use the first estimation in Lemma 2.2; then, by Fubini's theorem and the assumptions (HYP₁)

with (HYP₂), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \|Q\varpi\|_{1,\rho_1} = \int_0^{+\infty} |Q\varpi(\kappa)|e^{-\rho_1\kappa}d\kappa \\
 \leq & \int_0^{+\infty} \int_s^{+\infty} \frac{e^{(\rho-\rho_1)\kappa}}{\rho^\gamma}d\kappa \left\{ \ell|\varpi(s)| + \frac{\rho M_2}{\Gamma(1-\gamma)} + \rho(\ell'+1)D_{0+}^\gamma|\varpi| \right\} e^{-\rho s}ds + \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1\kappa}M_1d\kappa \\
 & + \int_0^{+\infty} \int_s^{+\infty} \frac{e^{(\rho-\rho_1)\kappa}}{\rho^\gamma}d\kappa \left\{ M_1 \right\} e^{-\rho s}ds + |\varpi_0| \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1\kappa}\rho^{-\gamma}e^{\rho\kappa}d\kappa + \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1\kappa}\ell'|\varpi(\kappa)|d\kappa \\
 & + \frac{1}{|1-\sum_{i=0}^m\sigma_i\xi_i^{\gamma-1}|} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1\kappa}\kappa^{\gamma-1}\rho^{-\gamma}e^{\rho(1-s)}d\kappa \left\{ \ell|\varpi(s)| + M_1 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + \frac{\rho M_2}{\Gamma(1-\gamma)} + \rho(\ell'+1)D_{0+}^\gamma|\varpi| \right\} ds + |\mathcal{E}(1, \varpi(1))| + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i|\mathcal{E}(\xi_i, \varpi(\xi_i)) \right] \\
 & + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1\kappa}\kappa^{\gamma-1}\rho^{-\gamma}e^{\rho(\xi_i-s)}d\kappa \left\{ \ell|\varpi(s)| + M_1 \right. \\
 & \left. + \frac{\rho M_2}{\Gamma(1-\gamma)} + \rho(\ell'+1)D_{0+}^\gamma|\varpi| \right\} ds + \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1\kappa}\kappa^{\gamma-1}d\kappa \left\{ |\varpi_0| \left[\sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i|\rho^{-\gamma}e^{\rho\xi_i} + \rho^{-\gamma}e^\rho \right] \right\} \\
 \leq & \frac{1}{\rho^\gamma(\rho_1-\rho)} \left[\ell\|\varpi\|_{1,\rho_1} + \rho(\ell'+1)\|D_{0+}^\gamma\varpi\|_{1,\rho_1} + \frac{\rho M_2}{\rho_1\Gamma(1-\gamma)} + \frac{M_1}{\rho_1} + |\varpi_0| \right] + \ell'\|\varpi\|_{1,\rho_1} + \frac{M_1}{\rho_1} \\
 & + \frac{\Gamma(\gamma)}{|1-\sum_{i=0}^m\sigma_i\xi_i^{\gamma-1}|\rho_1^\gamma\rho^\gamma} \left[\left\{ \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i|e^{\rho\xi_i} + e^\rho \right\} \times \left\{ \ell\|\varpi\|_{1,\rho_1} + \rho(\ell'+1)\|D_{0+}^\gamma\varpi\|_{1,\rho_1} + \frac{M_2}{\Gamma(1-\gamma)} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + \frac{M_1}{\rho} \right\} + |\varpi_0| \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i|e^{\rho\xi_i} + |\varpi_0|e^\rho + \frac{\rho^\gamma\rho_1^\gamma}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \left\{ |\mathcal{E}(1, \varpi(1))| + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i|\mathcal{E}(\xi_i, \varpi(\xi_i)) \right\} \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, by (2.10) and Fubini's theorem, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \|D_{0+}^{\gamma} \mathcal{Q}\varpi\|_{1,\rho_1} = \int_0^{+\infty} |D_{0+}^{\gamma} \mathcal{Q}\varpi(\kappa)| e^{-\rho_1 \kappa} d\kappa \\
 & \leq \int_0^{+\infty} e^{(\rho-\rho_1)\kappa} \int_0^{\kappa} \left\{ |\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, 0)| + |\mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^{\gamma} \varpi(s))| \right\} e^{-\rho s} ds d\kappa \\
 & \quad + \int_0^{+\infty} e^{(\rho-\rho_1)\kappa} \int_0^{\kappa} \left\{ |\mathcal{F}(s, 0)| \right\} e^{-\rho s} ds d\kappa + |\varpi_0| \int_0^{+\infty} e^{(\rho-\rho_1)\kappa} d\kappa \\
 & \quad + \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1 \kappa} D_{0+}^{\gamma} |\mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) - \mathcal{E}(\kappa, 0)| d\kappa + \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1 \kappa} D_{0+}^{\gamma} |\mathcal{E}(\kappa, 0)| d\kappa \\
 & \leq \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\rho_1 - \rho} \left\{ \ell |\varpi(s)| + \frac{\rho M_2}{\Gamma(1-\gamma)} + \rho(\ell' + 1) D_{0+}^{\gamma} |\varpi(s)| \right\} e^{-\rho_1 s} ds + \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\rho_1 - \rho} \left\{ |\mathcal{F}(s, 0)| \right\} e^{-\rho_1 s} ds \\
 & \quad + \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1 \kappa} D_{0+}^{\gamma} |\mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) - \mathcal{E}(s, 0)| d\kappa + \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1 \kappa} D_{0+}^{\gamma} |\mathcal{E}(\kappa, 0)| d\kappa + \frac{|\varpi_0|}{\rho_1 - \rho} \\
 & = \frac{\ell}{\rho_1 - \rho} \|\varpi\|_{1,\rho_1} + \frac{\rho_1 \ell' + \rho}{\rho_1 - \rho} \|D_{0+}^{\gamma} \varpi\|_{1,\rho_1} + \frac{\rho M_2}{\rho_1 \Gamma(1-\gamma)} + \frac{M_1 + |\varpi_0|}{\rho_1(\rho_1 - \rho)}. \tag{3.12}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|\mathcal{Q}\varpi\|_{W_{\rho_1,0+}^{\gamma,1}} & = \|\mathcal{Q}\varpi\|_{1,\rho_1} + \|D_{0+}^{\gamma} \mathcal{Q}\varpi\|_{1,\rho_1} \\
 & \leq \left\{ \frac{(1 + \rho^{\gamma})\ell}{\rho^{\gamma}(\rho_1 - \rho)} + \ell' + \frac{\sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| e^{\rho \xi_i} + e^{\rho}}{|1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}| \rho_1^{\gamma} \rho^{\gamma}} \ell \Gamma(\gamma) \right\} \|\varpi\|_{1,\rho_1} \\
 & \quad + \left\{ \frac{\rho(\ell' + 1) + \rho^{\gamma}(\rho_1 \ell + \rho)}{\rho^{\gamma}(\rho_1 - \rho)} + \frac{\sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| e^{\rho \xi_i} + e^{\rho}}{|1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}| \rho_1^{\gamma} \rho^{\gamma}} \rho(\ell' + 1) \Gamma(\gamma) \right\} \|D_{0+}^{\gamma} \varpi\|_{1,\rho_1} \\
 & \quad + \frac{\Gamma(\gamma)}{|1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}| \rho_1^{\gamma} \rho^{\gamma}} \left[\left\{ \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| e^{\rho \xi_i} + e^{\rho} \right\} \left\{ \frac{M_1}{\rho} + \frac{M_2}{\Gamma(1-\gamma)} \right\} + |\varpi_0| \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| e^{\rho \xi_i} + |\varpi_0| e^{\rho} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \frac{\rho^{\gamma} \rho_1^{\gamma}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \left\{ |\mathcal{E}(1, \varpi(1))| + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| |\mathcal{E}(\xi_i, \varpi(\xi_i))| \right\} \right] \\
 & \quad + \frac{1 + \rho^{\gamma} + \rho^{\gamma}(\rho_1 - \rho)}{\rho_1 \rho^{\gamma}(\rho_1 - \rho)} M_1 + \frac{\rho + \rho \rho^{\gamma}(\rho_1 - \rho)}{\rho_1 \rho^{\gamma}(\rho_1 - \rho) \Gamma(1-\gamma)} M_2 + \frac{|\varpi_0|}{\rho_1(\rho_1 - \rho)} \\
 & \leq \max\{\delta'_1; \delta'_2\} \|\varpi\|_{W_{\rho_1,0+}^{\gamma,1}} + \delta'_0. \tag{3.13}
 \end{aligned}$$

Using the assumption (3.9), we obtain: $\|\mathcal{Q}\varpi(\kappa)\|_{W_{\rho_1,0+}^{\gamma,1}} \leq r$, which implies that $\mathcal{Q}(B_r) \subset B_r$.

Second step: We shall show that $\mathcal{Q} : B_r \rightarrow B_r$ is a contraction.

In view of the assumption (HY \mathbb{P}_2), we have for any $\varpi, \omega \in B_r$ and for each $\kappa \in \mathbb{R}_+$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \|Q\varpi - Q\omega\|_{1,\rho_1} = \int_0^{+\infty} |Q\varpi(\kappa) - Q\omega(\kappa)|e^{-\rho_1\kappa} d\kappa \\
 \leq & \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1\kappa} \int_0^\kappa \rho^{-\gamma} e^{\rho(\kappa-s)} \left\{ |\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, \omega)| + |\mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s)) - \mathcal{G}(s, \omega(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \omega(s))| \right\} ds d\kappa \\
 & + \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1\kappa} |\mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) - \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \omega(\kappa))| d\kappa \\
 & + \frac{1}{|1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}|} \left[\int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1\kappa} \kappa^{\gamma-1} \int_0^1 \rho^{-\gamma} e^{\rho(1-s)} \left\{ |\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, \omega)| \right. \right. \\
 & + |\mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s)) - \mathcal{G}(s, \omega(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \omega(s))| \left. \left. \right\} ds d\kappa \right. \\
 & + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1\kappa} \kappa^{\gamma-1} \int_0^{\xi_i} \rho^{-\gamma} e^{\rho(\xi_i-s)} \left\{ |\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, \omega)| \right. \\
 & + |\mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \varpi(s)) - \mathcal{G}(s, \omega(s), D_{0+}^\gamma \omega(s))| \left. \right\} ds d\kappa \left. \right] \\
 \leq & \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\rho^\gamma(\rho_1 - \rho)} \left\{ \ell |\varpi(s) - \omega(s)| + \rho(\ell' + 1) D_{0+}^\gamma |\varpi(s) - \omega(s)| \right\} e^{-\rho_1 s} ds + \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1 \kappa} \ell' |\varpi(s) - \omega(s)| ds \\
 & + \frac{1}{|1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}|} \left[\rho^{-\gamma} \left(\frac{\gamma-1}{\rho_1} \right)^{\gamma-1} e^{\rho+1-\gamma} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1 s} \left\{ \ell |\varpi(s) - \omega(s)| + \rho(\ell' + 1) D_{0+}^\gamma |\varpi(s) - \omega(s)| \right\} ds \right. \\
 & + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| \rho^{-\gamma} \left(\frac{\gamma-1}{\rho_1} \right)^{\gamma-1} e^{\rho \xi_i + 1 - \gamma} \xi_i \int_0^\infty e^{-\rho_1 s} \left\{ \ell |\varpi(s) - \omega(s)| + \rho(\ell' + 1) D_{0+}^\gamma |\varpi(s) - \omega(s)| \right\} ds \left. \right] \\
 \leq & \left\{ \frac{\ell + \rho^\gamma(\rho_1 - \rho)\ell'}{\rho^\gamma(\rho_1 - \rho)} + \frac{\rho^{-\gamma} \left(\frac{\gamma-1}{\rho_1} \right)^{\gamma-1} e^{1-\gamma} [e^\rho + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| e^{\rho \xi_i} \xi_i]}{|1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}|} \right\} \|\varpi - \omega\|_{1,\rho_1} \\
 & + \left\{ \frac{1}{\rho^\gamma(\rho_1 - \rho)} + \frac{\rho^{-\gamma} \left(\frac{\gamma-1}{\rho_1} \right)^{\gamma-1} e^{1-\gamma} [e^\rho + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| e^{\rho \xi_i} \xi_i]}{|1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}|} \right\} \rho(\ell' + 1) \|D_{0+}^\gamma (\varpi - \omega)\|_{1,\rho_1}, \tag{3.14}
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \|D_{0+}^{\gamma}(\mathcal{Q}\varpi - \mathcal{Q}\omega)\|_{L_{1,\rho_1}} = \int_0^{+\infty} |D_{0+}^{\gamma}\mathcal{Q}\varpi(\kappa) - D_{0+}^{\gamma}\mathcal{Q}\omega(\kappa)|e^{-\rho_1\kappa}d\kappa \\
 & \leq \int_0^{+\infty} e^{(\rho-\rho_1)\kappa} \int_0^{\kappa} \left\{ |\mathcal{F}(s, \varpi(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, \omega(s))| \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + |\mathcal{G}(s, \varpi(s), D_{0+}^{\gamma}\varpi(s)) - \mathcal{G}(s, \omega(s), D_{0+}^{\gamma}\omega(s))| \right\} e^{-\rho s} ds d\kappa \\
 & \quad + \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1\kappa} |D_{0+}^{\gamma}\mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi(\kappa)) - D_{0+}^{\gamma}\mathcal{E}(\kappa, \omega(\kappa))| d\kappa \\
 & \leq \int_0^{+\infty} e^{(\rho-\rho_1)\kappa} \int_0^{\kappa} \left\{ \ell|\varpi(s) - \omega(s)| + \rho(\ell' + 1)|D_{0+}^{\gamma}\varpi(s) - D_{0+}^{\gamma}\omega(s)| \right\} e^{-\rho s} ds d\kappa \\
 & \quad + \ell' \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\rho_1\kappa} |\varpi(\kappa) - \omega(\kappa)| d\kappa \\
 & \leq \frac{\ell + \ell'}{\rho_1 - \rho} \|\varpi - \omega\|_{1,\rho_1} + \frac{\rho(\ell' + 1)}{\rho_1 - \rho} \|D_{0+}^{\gamma}(\varpi - \omega)\|_{1,\rho_1}. \tag{3.15}
 \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \|\mathcal{Q}\varpi - \mathcal{Q}\omega\|_{W_{\rho_1,0+}^{\gamma,1}} \\
 & \leq \left\{ \frac{\ell(1 + \rho^{\gamma}) + \rho^{\gamma}(1 + \rho_1 - \rho)\ell'}{\rho^{\gamma}(\rho_1 - \rho)} + \frac{\rho^{-\gamma} \left(\frac{\gamma-1}{\rho_1}\right)^{\gamma-1} e^{1-\gamma} [e^{\rho} + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| e^{\rho\xi_i} \xi_i]}{|1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}|} \ell \right\} \|\varpi - \omega\|_{1,\rho_1} \\
 & \quad + \left\{ \frac{1 + \rho\rho^{\gamma}(\ell' + 1)}{\rho^{\gamma}(\rho_1 - \rho)} + \frac{\rho^{-\gamma} \left(\frac{\gamma-1}{\rho_1}\right)^{\gamma-1} e^{1-\gamma} [e^{\rho} + \sum_{i=0}^m |\sigma_i| e^{\rho\xi_i} \xi_i]}{|1 - \sum_{i=0}^m \sigma_i \xi_i^{\gamma-1}|} \right\} \rho(\ell' + 1) \|D_{0+}^{\gamma}(\varpi - \omega)\|_{1,\rho_1} \\
 & \leq \max\{\delta'_3, \delta'_4\} \|\varpi - \omega\|_{W_{\rho_1,0+}^{\gamma,1}}. \tag{3.16}
 \end{aligned}$$

By the inequality (3.7), it yields:

$$\|\mathcal{Q}\varpi - \mathcal{Q}\omega\|_{W_{\rho_1,0+}^{\gamma,1}} < \|\varpi - \omega\|_{W_{\rho_1,0+}^{\gamma,1}}, \text{ for all } \varpi, \omega \in W_{\rho_1,0+}^{\gamma,1}.$$

That means \mathcal{Q} is a contraction in $W_{\rho_1,0+}^{\gamma,1}$.

All the conditions of the Banach fixed point theorem are satisfied; therefore, there exists a unique solution $\varpi \in W_{\rho_1,0+}^{\gamma,1}$ such that $\mathcal{Q}\varpi = \varpi$. Thus, ϖ is the unique solution of problem (2.6) in $W_{\rho_1,0+}^{\gamma,1}$. \square

4 Examples

Example 4.1. Consider the following explicit form of problem (1.1) on the interval $\kappa \in [0, 1]$:

$$\begin{cases} D_{0+}^{\alpha} \left(\varpi(\kappa) + \frac{1}{10} \varpi(\kappa) \right) = \frac{1}{5} \varpi(\kappa) + e^{-3\kappa}, & \kappa \in [0, 1], \\ D_{0+}^{\alpha-1} \left(\varpi(0) + \frac{1}{10} \varpi(0) \right) = \varpi_0, \\ \varpi(1) = \sigma_0 \varpi(\xi_0) + \sigma_1 \varpi(\xi_1), \end{cases} \quad (4.1)$$

with the numerical parameters

$$\alpha = \frac{3}{2}, \quad \varpi_0 = 1, \quad m = 1, \quad \sigma_0 = \frac{1}{4}, \quad \sigma_1 = \frac{1}{5}, \quad \xi_0 = \frac{1}{3}, \quad \xi_1 = \frac{2}{3}.$$

This corresponds to

$$\mathcal{F}(\kappa, \varpi) = \frac{1}{5} \varpi + e^{-3\kappa}, \quad \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi) = \frac{1}{10} \varpi(\kappa).$$

For any $\varpi, \omega \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\kappa \in [0, 1]$,

$$|\mathcal{F}(\kappa, \varpi) - \mathcal{F}(\kappa, \omega)| = \frac{1}{5} |\varpi - \omega|, \quad |\mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi) - \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \omega)| = \frac{1}{10} |\varpi - \omega|,$$

so the Lipschitz constants are $\ell = \frac{1}{5}$ and $\ell' = \frac{1}{10}$. Moreover,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}(\cdot, 0) &= e^{-3\kappa} \in L^1([0, 1]), & \int_0^1 e^{-3\kappa} d\kappa &= \frac{1-e^{-3}}{3} < \infty, \\ \mathcal{F}(\cdot, 0) &\in L_{1,1}([0, 1]), & \mathcal{E}(\cdot, 0) &= 0 \in L_{1,1}([0, 1]). \end{aligned}$$

Substituting these values into the expressions for δ'_3 and δ'_4 (see (3.3)–(3.4)) gives

$$\delta'_3 \approx 0.4342, \quad \delta'_4 \approx 0.9626, \quad \implies \quad \max\{\delta'_3, \delta'_4\} \approx 0.9626 < 1,$$

which satisfies the contractive condition required by Theorem 3.1 (Banach contraction principle). To illustrate the validity of the hypotheses used in the existence and uniqueness analysis, we provide a graphical representation of the functions involved in conditions (HYP₁) and (HYP₂). These plots confirm the boundedness and Lipschitz-type behavior required by the theoretical framework.

Example 4.2. Consider the following explicit form of problem (1.1) on the interval $\kappa \in [0, 3]$:

$$\begin{cases} D_{0+}^{\alpha} \left(\varpi(\kappa) + \frac{1}{8} \varpi(\kappa) \right) = \frac{2}{9} \varpi(\kappa) + e^{-2\kappa}, & \kappa \in [0, 3], \\ D_{0+}^{\alpha-1} \left(\varpi(0) + \frac{1}{8} \varpi(0) \right) = \varpi_0, \\ \varpi(3) = \sigma_0 \varpi(\xi_0) + \sigma_1 \varpi(\xi_1) + \sigma_2 \varpi(\xi_2) + \sigma_3 \varpi(\xi_3), \end{cases} \quad (4.2)$$

Figure 1: Graphical illustration of the functions involved in hypotheses (HYP₁) and (HYP₂).

with the numerical parameters

$$\alpha = \frac{4}{3}, \quad \varpi_0 = 2, \quad m = 3, \quad \sigma_0 = \frac{1}{6}, \quad \sigma_1 = \frac{1}{7}, \quad \sigma_2 = \frac{1}{8}, \quad \sigma_3 = \frac{1}{9},$$

$$\xi_0 = \frac{1}{2}, \quad \xi_1 = 1, \quad \xi_2 = \frac{3}{2}, \quad \xi_3 = 2.$$

This corresponds to

$$\mathcal{F}(\kappa, \varpi) = \frac{2}{9} \varpi + e^{-2\kappa}, \quad \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi) = \frac{1}{8} \varpi.$$

For any $\varpi, \omega \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\kappa \in [0, 3)$,

$$|\mathcal{F}(\kappa, \varpi) - \mathcal{F}(\kappa, \omega)| = \frac{2}{9} |\varpi - \omega|, \quad |\mathcal{E}(\kappa, \varpi) - \mathcal{E}(\kappa, \omega)| = \frac{1}{8} |\varpi - \omega|,$$

so the Lipschitz constants are $\ell = \frac{2}{9}$ and $\ell' = \frac{1}{8}$. Moreover,

$$\mathcal{F}(\cdot, 0) = e^{-2\kappa} \in L^1([0, 3)), \quad \int_0^3 e^{-2\kappa} d\kappa = \frac{1-e^{-6}}{2} < \infty,$$

$$\mathcal{F}(\cdot, 0) \in L_{1,1}([0, 3)), \quad \mathcal{E}(\cdot, 0) = 0 \in L_{1,1}([0, 3)).$$

Substituting these values into the expressions for δ'_3 and δ'_4 (see (3.3)–(3.4)) gives

Figure 2: Graphical representation of the functions appearing in hypotheses (HYP₁) and (HYP₂).

$$\delta'_3 \approx 0.5124, \quad \delta'_4 \approx 0.8731, \quad \implies \quad \max\{\delta'_3, \delta'_4\} \approx 0.8731 < 1,$$

which satisfies the contractive condition required by Theorem 3.1 (Banach contraction principle). Clearly, the conditions (HYP₁) and (HYP₂) hold with $\max\{\delta'_3, \delta'_4\} \approx 0.8731 < 1$. Hence, all hypotheses of Theorem 3.1 are satisfied. Thus, problem (4.2) admits a unique solution. To validate the hypotheses in the existence and uniqueness analysis, we present graphs of the functions in conditions (HYP₁) and (HYP₂), confirming the required boundedness and Lipschitz properties.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Authors contributions

All authors have made equal contributions. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Data Availability

No datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.

Consent to publish declaration

Not applicable

Ethics declaration

Not applicable

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